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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>This report outlines the design, development, and sustainability plan for a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) within the UP2030 project, targeting city practitioners. The MOOC aims to integrate climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice into urban planning practices. Key elements discussed include the program's structure, learning objectives, pedagogical approach, and supplementary content.</p> <p>The implementation plan provides a timeline beginning with the platform's technical development in July 2024, followed by the production of theoretical, technical, and case study video capsules. The sustainability plan focuses on ensuring long-term viability through platform integration, potential funding mechanisms, and regular content updates. By emphasizing accessibility, practical relevance, and alignment with the 5UPs framework, the MOOC serves as a comprehensive resource for sustainable urban development. This report serves as a guide for the subsequent phases of the MOOC's production and dissemination.</p>			

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Executive summary

The training program aims to empower city practitioners with comprehensive knowledge, skills, and tools essential for integrating principles of climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice for urban planning practices. Additionally, it seeks to inspire them with a systematic process based on the 5UPs approach, which is at the center of the UP2030 project. The 5UPs approach is a step-by-step framework made up of five consecutive stages: UP-Dating, UP-Skilling, UP-Grading, UP-Scaling, and UP-Taking. Notably, the program will accentuate the tools and methodologies developed during the project, showcasing concrete examples from collaboration within the 10 city partners.

Delivered as a massive open online course (MOOC), the training program will consist of highly comprehensive video capsules. Its structure encompasses a methodical curriculum covering theoretical foundations, technical aspects, and case studies. While primarily disseminated through the MOOC platform, the videos will also be independently accessible, catering to individuals with specific interests or learning requirements.

Structured into three modules, the program begins with theoretical knowledge alignment, followed by methodological steps focusing on capacity building and implementation. These steps are reorganized around the 5UPs approach to resonate with the project's identity and narrative, and to capitalize on the diverse outcomes of the UP2030 project.

The program commences introducing the training methodology and an overview of the UP2030 project. It aims to guide participants in understanding the "what" before delving into the "how" by facilitating the development of urban visions and goals, introducing the concept of adaptive pathways, and providing inspirations tailored to cities contexts. The subsequent capsules follow the 5UPs process, supported by tutorials about the useful tools, illustration of urban transformation and governance processes, and showcasing the project cities' work.

The first module focuses on **aligning knowledge on the project's main concepts and explaining UP2030's approach**. It includes most of the theoretical content about the project, high-quality, accessible courses on major concepts related to resilient, climate-neutral, and socially just urban transformations, and emphasizes identifying needs and barriers while building a vision. The second module emphasizes **building capacities for urban planning and design transformation pathways**. It provides guidance and technical knowledge to upskill the entire stakeholder ecosystem, from urban practitioners to citizens, supporting the implementation of transformation prototypes at a suitable scale and updating urban planning practices. The third module focuses on **extending solutions across scales and integrating them across sectors**. It addresses the need for updating governance arrangements and aligning projects with financial resources. Designed in coordination with ICLEI's Upscaling Service Platform, this module supports knowledge uptake and encourages alumni to share the program within their networks, join a community of practice, and promote the mission's scope and impact.

This deliverable marks the initial phase of the training program's development, focusing on its design, methodology, purpose, alignment with UP2030 project outcomes, and sustainability and contingency plan. Subsequent steps will involve the production of the MOOC and its video capsules. Given the interconnected nature of the training program with the project's results and progress, a significant portion of its content remains to be finalized or may evolve as the project develops, with continuous updates planned throughout its implementation.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with UCCRN, TUD, UCAM, ICLEI, RCitics, Pilot Cities and WPs. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>WP5 – UP-SCALING – Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making.</p> <p>D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualization in the project cities.</p> <p>D3.6 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 1.</p> <p>D6.8 – Exploitation & Sustainability Planning & Activities Report 1.</p>	<p>WP5 – UP-SCALING – Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making.</p> <p>D5.3 – UP2030 Service Platform</p>

The primary target group for this deliverable is ourselves at UIC, as this deliverable represents the first step in the development of the MOOC. UIC will be responsible for the subsequent production phase, which will be addressed in D5.7 – Online Learning Programme materials. Additionally, this deliverable will benefit WP5, which focuses on strategic learning and the project legacy.

At this stage, the work has been valuable for city partners by providing knowledge alignment through masterclasses. As the project progresses, it will continue to support partners by producing training videos. Once the MOOC is ready, it will be disseminated through various partner platforms and networks, independent video dissemination, events, collaborations with other projects, and by encouraging participant advocacy.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AMS	Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
Fraunhofer	Fraunhofer IAO
C40	C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group
CRT	City Resilience Training
D	Deliverable
GA	Grant Agreement
GIZ	German Agency for International Cooperation
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NBS	Nature Based Solution
PED	Positive Energy District
RCities	Resilient Cities
RMIT	Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
TUD	Delft University of Technology
TUM	Technical University of Munich
TUMI	Transformative Urban Mobility Initiative
UAB	Autonomous University of Barcelona
UBC	University of British Columbia
UCAM	University of Cambridge

UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network
UCL	University College London
UN	United Nations
UNDRR	UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UNECE	UN Economic Commission for Europe
UNEP	UN Environmental Programme
UNIL	Lausanne University
UPV	Plytechnic University of Valencia
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
WP	Work package
WRI	World Resource Institute
WRU	Wageningen University & Research
WWF	World Wildlife Fund
ZHAW	Zurich University of Applied Sciences

1 Introduction

The development of this training program marks a significant step in bridging the gap between academic advancements and practical urban planning. The primary aim is to empower city practitioners with the comprehensive knowledge, skills, and tools necessary for integrating principles of climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice into their urban planning practices. This report focuses on the first phase of the massive open online course (MOOC) development, detailing its purpose, design, program, implementation plan, and sustainability plan. The subsequent phases, including the production of the MOOC and its videos, will be addressed in future deliverables.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this training program is multifaceted, addressing both the needs of city practitioners and the broader goals of sustainable urban development. One of the main objectives is to make cutting-edge academic knowledge highly accessible to city practitioners, who may lack the time or resources to stay updated with the latest developments in their field. By offering comprehensive, up-to-date knowledge, technical tools, and practical solutions, the program aims to equip practitioners with the confidence and competence to apply these innovations in their daily work.

A critical gap exists between the solutions developed in the academic or technical spheres and the practical application of these solutions in real life. This training program seeks to fill that gap by providing hyper-accessible (free, flexible, short and synthetic yet complete modules, available in different languages,..) content that makes complex concepts and tools easy to understand and implement. The emphasis is on delivering content that is not only informative but also actionable, ensuring that practitioners can readily apply what they learn to real-world urban planning challenges. For instance, technical solutions introduced in the course are provided with in-depth tutorials and case examples, enabling practitioners to implement these tools effectively in their own projects.

Figure 1: UP2030 Three pillars approach representation.

Moreover, the program emphasizes a holistic approach that integrates the three pillars of resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice (Figure 1). These elements are crucial for creating sustainable and equitable urban environments. By adopting this holistic approach, the program aims to break down silos, encouraging an integrated perspective that addresses the multifaceted challenges of urban planning.

Collaboration with the 10 city partners is a cornerstone of the training program, providing real-life examples and case studies that illustrate the practical application of the concepts and tools covered in the courses. These partnerships ensure that the training is grounded in real-world experiences and challenges, making it highly relevant and impactful for practitioners. Additionally, collaboration with technical partners and solutions providers adds a crucial technical dimension to the training, ensuring that

The program aims to guide practitioners through a step-by-step methodology designed to facilitate comprehensive urban planning. This methodology is based on the 5UPs framework, which includes the stages of UP-Dating, UP-Skilling, UP-Grading, UP-Scaling, and UP-Taking. This structured approach is integral to the UP2030 Horizon project, aligning with its methodology and outcomes.

Moreover, the program emphasizes a holistic approach that integrates the three pillars of resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice (Figure 1). These elements are crucial for creating sustainable and equitable urban environments.

participants gain practical knowledge of cutting-edge tools and methodologies. In summary, this report outlines the purpose and scope of the MOOC development, emphasizing its role in making advanced knowledge and tools accessible to city practitioners. It promotes a holistic approach to urban planning and bridges the gap between academic research and practical application.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 – Review and analysis of existing courses - including the state of the art of similar online courses and the gaps and opportunities
- ❖ Section 3 – MOOC program design: the learning objectives, the pedagogical approach, the program overview and structure and the potential additional content.
- ❖ Section 4 – Implementation plan: covers the timeline and contingency plan, the content resources and the current stage, the platform selection and the dissemination plan.
- ❖ Section 5 – Sustainability plan: financially, over the long-term and in the event of unforeseen circumstances.
- ❖ Section 6 - Next steps.
- ❖ Section 7 – Conclusion.
- ❖ Section 8 – Appendix.

1.3 Integration within the project

Deliverable 5.6 (D5.6) outlines the design and implementation plan for modules and methodologies, along with a sustainability plan for a learning program in MOOC format. This deliverable is closely linked with D5.7, responsible for producing and releasing the actual content and MOOC. Contributors to these tasks include UCCRN, TUD, UCAM, ICLEI, RCities, and Pilot Cities.

Integration of this task within the project occurs in two distinct phases. The first phase, during the project's development, involves collaboration with partners within the consortium. Activities during this phase include following the evolution of the project and other deliverables, identifying training needs, and creating content for knowledge alignment.

The second phase aims to contribute to the project's legacy and support its primary objective of facilitating urban transition processes for European cities. This phase involves ensuring that the training provided presents, explains, organizes, and connects every product of UP2030 (tools, processes, theoretical frameworks, etc.) with practitioners working within cities on similar topics. To achieve this, the design of the training must be integrated with the globality of the project. This is accomplished through collaboration with task leaders, the contributors mentioned above, and numerous meetings and workshops since the beginning of the project, ensuring its relevance and applicability beyond the consortium.

As several platforms and products will be developed within the project, it is crucial to coordinate and link with other task leaders to maintain coherence and ensure the best user experience for those navigating between different UP2030 products.

2 Review and analysis of existing courses

This section delves into a comprehensive review and analysis of existing courses with a specific focus on the three pillars of UP2030: climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice. These pillars form the foundation of this training program, ensuring that city practitioners are equipped with holistic and impactful strategies for urban planning.

The research scope intentionally excludes a primary focus on "smart cities," as initially suggested in the Grant Agreement (GA). While technology plays a vital role in modern urban development and numerous technological solutions will be integrated into the course and the project, an overemphasis on technology-driven solutions often overlooks the broader social and environmental implications. Such techno-solutionist approaches can lead to scenarios where the environmental costs of technologies, including their significant energy consumption, are ignored. Additionally, while smart city initiatives rely heavily on efficiency, online monitoring, and control for effective management, they often do not prioritize the foundational pillars of greening and sustainability. Therefore, rather than centering solely on smart city principles, this program adopts a holistic approach based on the three pillars mentioned above. This approach allows for the inclusion of critical aspects such as equity, inclusivity, community engagement, cultural heritage, and wide-scope sustainability.

The following subsections will provide an in-depth state of the art review of similar online courses, identifying current gaps and opportunities for improvement in this field.

2.1 State of the art of similar online courses

In assessing the landscape of existing online courses related to carbon neutrality, resilience and social justice in cities, this section explores the key platforms and organizations that offer relevant trainings. It aims to identify the most pertinent and innovative courses currently available, providing insights into the prevailing trends and methodologies employed in the field. This analysis will help to highlight best practices and potential gaps that our program can address to ensure comprehensive and effective training for city practitioners.

2.1.1 Main learning platforms

In the realm of online education, several key platforms stand out for their extensive offerings of MOOCs relevant to urban planning, climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice. Each platform brings its unique strengths and focuses, catering to different learning needs and preferences. While many platforms offer valuable content, this section will present the four main platforms that are most relevant for these topics: Coursera, edX, Udemy, and FutureLearn.

The most relevant courses from each platform are presented directly following the platform's section. All relevant courses are summarised in Appendix 1.

Table 1: Comparison of platforms general informations.

Platform	Coursera	edX	FutureLearn	Udemy
Launched in	2012	2012	2013	2010
Courses	8500+	4600+	1300+	213.000+
Users	113 million+	86 million+	18 million+	57 million+
Partners	275+	260+	260+	70+
Languages	30+	30+	15+	75+
Main topics	Business, Technology, Data Science, Health, Social Sciences	Computer Science, Engineering, Humanities, Data Science, Business	Business & Management, Healthcare & Medicine, Science, Engineering & Maths, Teaching	Development, Business, Finance & Accounting, IT & Software, Office Productivity
Price range	Free to €90 for individual courses. Specializations and professional certificates typically range from €35 to €70 per month. Full degree programs can range from €13,500 to €22,500.	Free to €270 for individual courses. Verified certificates range from €45 to €270. MicroMasters programs can cost between €540 and €1,350. Full degree programs can range from €9,000 to €22,500.	Free access to course content during the course run. Certificates of achievement range from €35 to €80. Microcredentials and expert tracks can range from €450 to €1,350.	€9 to €180 for individual courses, with frequent discounts lowering prices significantly.
Average price	Most content available for free. Around €45 per month for specializations and professional certificates.	Most content available for free. Around €90 for verified certificates.	Most content available for free. Around €60 for certificates of achievement.	No free content. Around €10 to €18 during promotional periods.

Coursera

Figure 2: Coursera platform. Source: [Coursera](https://www.coursera.org).

Coursera collaborates with top universities and organizations worldwide to deliver high-quality courses across various disciplines. It offers a robust selection of courses on urban planning and sustainability, often featuring interactive content, peer assessments, and access to a community of learners. Coursera's model allows for both free course access and paid options for certification, making it suitable for both casual learners and professionals seeking formal credentials. Its strong academic partnerships ensure that the courses are research-driven and of high quality.

Particularity and differences: Coursera is distinguished by its structured learning paths, including specializations and full degree programs. This makes it particularly appealing to learners seeking a more formal educational experience. Compared to Udemy, Coursera's content is more consistent in quality due to its collaboration with reputable institutions (top universities like Yale and Stanford, leading companies like Google and IBM and more relevant institutions like Lausanne Universities UNIL and EPFL, Lund University, Johns Hopkins University and many more). Unlike FutureLearn, which focuses on social learning, Coursera emphasizes interactive content and peer assessments within a more formal academic structure.

Table 2: Summary of relevant online courses on Coursera.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Cities and Consumption: Urban Sustainability and the Sharing Economy	Lund University	Cross-cutting, Economy, Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities, Climate and Change: Pathways and Opportunities	Lund University	Carbon neutrality, Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Economy, Sust. Urb.
link	Climate change and Indigenous People and local communities	UAB	Climate Change, Governance, Social Justice
link	Gestion des infrastructures urbaines - partie 1	EPFL	Cross-cutting, Energy, Mobility, Resilience
link	Greening the Economy: Sustainable Cities	Lund University, WWF, ICLEI	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Economy, Sust. Urb.
link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 1	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Health, Resilience
link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 2 : Theories, models and tools	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Governance, Health, Resilience
link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 3 : Design and policies	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Governance, Health, Smart Cities
link	Innovative Governance of Large Urban Systems	EPFL	Cross-cutting, Economy, Governance, Regenerative
link	Planning for Climate Change in African Cities	Erasmus University Rotterdam	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience
link	Street Experiments for Sustainable and Resilient cities	TUM, EIT	Cross-cutting, Governance, Mobility, Resilience, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Neighborhoods	Johns Hopkins University	Cross-cutting, Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Regional Principles, Planning and Transportation	Johns Hopkins University	Governance, Growth, Mobility, Sust. Urb.

link	Sustainable Transportation Networks and Streetscapes	Johns Hopkins University	Growth, Mobility, Resilience, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Urban Regeneration	Bocconi University	Carbon neutrality, Economy, Governance, Regenerative, Resilience, Social Justice
link	Transportation, Sustainable Buildings, Green Construction	Johns Hopkins University	Carbon neutrality, Social Justice, Sust. Archi., Sust. Urb.
link	Urban Climate Governance: Towards 1.5° Celsius Alignment	Lund University, WWF	Cross-cutting, Energy, Governance, Mobility, Sust. Urb.
link	Urban Nature: Connecting Cities, Sustainability and Innovation	Lund University	Economy, Governance, NBS
link	Urbanisation and Health - Promoting Sustainable Solutions	University of Copenhagen, EIT, Politecnica Madrid, University of Coimbra	Cross-cutting, Health, NBS, Social Justice

edX

Figure 3: edX platform interface. Source: [edX](#).

Founded by Harvard University and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), edX is a leading platform providing a diverse array of courses from renowned institutions (such as Harvard University, the

MIT, TUD, Wageningen University (WUR), the SDG academy and many others). It emphasizes open access to education and offers numerous courses on environmental sustainability, urban resilience, and social justice. edX courses often include in-depth theoretical content, practical case studies, and opportunities for real-world application through project-based learning. The platform's commitment to open-source education means that many courses are available for free, with optional paid certificates.

Particularity and differences: edX stands out with its strong emphasis on open-source education and structured, university-style courses, similar to Coursera but with a greater focus on providing a wide range of free educational content. This approach ensures broad accessibility and inclusion, allowing more learners worldwide to benefit from high-quality education. Unlike Udemy, which features courses created by individual instructors, edX courses are typically developed by academic institutions, ensuring a higher level of consistency and credibility. Compared to FutureLearn, edX offers more self-paced options, allowing learners to progress at their own pace.

Table 3: Summary of relevant online courses on edX.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Building Inclusive Cities: Tackling Urban Inequality and Segregation	TUD	Social Justice
link	Built environment sustainability assessment	UPV	Cross-cutting, Economy, Energy, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities and Climate Change: Mitigation and Adaptation	MIT	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Health, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities and the Challenge of Sustainable Development	SDG academy	Sust. Urb.
link	CitiesX: The Past, Present and Future of Urban Life	Harvard University	Cross-cutting, Governance, Mobility, Social Justice
link	Co-Creating Sustainable Cities	TUD, WUR	Energy, Food, Governance, Sust. Urb.
link	Co-Creating Sustainable Cities	TUD, WUR	Cross-cutting, Energy, Food, Governance, Mobility
link	Designing a Climate-Neutral World: An Introduction	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Sust. Urb.
link	Designing a Climate-Neutral World: Taking Action	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Governance

link	Designing Climate-Neutral Buildings and Transport	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Mobility, Sust. Archi., Sust. Urb.
link	Designing Climate-Neutral Industry and Electricity Generation	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy
link	Ecodesign for Cities and Suburbs	UBC	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Environmental Gamechanger – Lead the Way to Sustainable Development	WUR	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Food and Nutrition Security in Urbanising Landscapes	WUR, UN environment, Landscape academy	Cross-cutting, Food, Governance, Resilience, Sust. Urb.
link	Global housing design	TUD	Sust. Archi.
link	Nature-based Urban Regeneration	RWTH Aachen University	Governance, NBS, Regenerative
link	New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges	TUD	Cross-cutting, Social Justice
link	Passive Urban Cooling Solutions	World Bank Group	Cross-cutting, Governance, NBS, Resilience
link	Professional Certificate in Climate-Neutral World: Theory, Applications and Taking Action	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Energy, Governance, Mobility
link	Reclaiming Broken Places: Introduction to Civic Ecology	Cornell University	Biodiversity, Cross-cutting, Governance, Social Justice
link	Rethink the city: New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges	TUD	Cross-cutting, Social Justice
link	Shaping Urban Futures	SDG academy	Cross-cutting, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Smart and Sustainable Cities: New Ways of Digitalization & Governance	TUD	Governance, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Cities	SDG academy	Cross-cutting, Governance, Health, Resilience, Social Justice

link	Sustainable Urban Development	TUD & WUR, AMS	Cross-cutting, Growth, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Urban Environments	Trinity College	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience, Sust. Urb.
link	The Transition to the Decarbonised Economy of Tomorrow	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy
link	Urban Ecology Design	TUD	Biodiversity, NBS, Regenerative
link	Urban Rewilding: Restore Your Local Ecosystem	WUR	Biodiversity, Regenerative
link	Urban Upgrading for Inclusion, Sustainability and Resilience in a time of Global Pandemics	World Bank Group	Governance, Health, Resilience, Social Justice
link	Vision 2030	ZHAW	Cross-cutting, Food, Growth, Health, Resilience, Smart Cities, Social Justice

FutureLearn

Figure 4: FutureLearn platform. Source: [FutureLearn](#).

FutureLearn partners with various academic institutions and industry leaders to offer a wide range of courses. Its approach is characterized by a focus on social learning, encouraging interaction and discussion among participants. FutureLearn provides several courses related to urban development, climate action,

and community engagement, emphasizing collaborative learning and practical implementation. The platform often features scheduled course runs, which foster a sense of community and structured learning, contrasting with the more self-paced models of Udemy.

Particularity and differences: FutureLearn's emphasis on social learning and scheduled course runs sets it apart from the other platforms. This model encourages a collaborative and interactive learning environment, where participants can engage with peers and instructors in real-time. Unlike Coursera and edX, which offer more self-paced and certification-focused courses, FutureLearn's structure supports a community-based learning experience. Additionally, while Udemy offers flexibility and a vast course library, FutureLearn's courses are more structured and often developed in partnership with academic institutions, ensuring a high level of educational quality.

Table 4: Summary of relevant online courses on FutureLearn.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Achieving Transitions to Zero Carbon Emissions and Sustainable Urban Mobility	UCL, ICLEI, EIT, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Bringing Urban Nature Into the Cities of Tomorrow	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	NBS, Resilience
link	Building Belonging in a Globalised and Mobile World	EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice
link	Changing Urban Travel Behaviour for a Low-Carbon Transition	RMIT, EIT	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Creating Ethical and Sustainable Cities at the Local Level	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Electrification of Urban Mobility: How to Get it Right	EIT	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Mobility
link	Equity in Informal STEM Learning: Using the Equity Compass	UCL	Governance, Social Justice
link	Ethical Cities: Shaping the Future of Your City	RMIT	Governance, Social Justice
link	Fostering Inclusive Citizen Engagement in Urban Development	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice

link	Introduction to Climate Justice and Equity	University of Glasgow	Cross-cutting, Economy, Energy, Food, Governance, Social Justice
link	Reducing Carbon Footprints: Taking Action for a Sustainable Future	Warwick University	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Governance
link	Smart Urban Green Infrastructure	EIT, ACCESS Aalto University	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Mobility, NBS, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Cities: Governing Urban Adaptation Under Climate Change	University of Groningen & Global Center on Adaptation	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience, Smart Cities, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	The Challenge of Clean Growth and Clean Cities	Manchester Metropolitan University	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Growth, Smart Cities
link	The New European Bauhaus: Concept, Movement, and Opportunities	EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, NBS, Sust. Urb.
link	Transforming Urban Mobility: Components of Transport Planning for Sustainable Cities	UCL, GIZ, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Transforming Urban Mobility: Introduction to Transport Planning for Sustainable Cities	UCL, GIZ, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Transit-Oriented Development for Climate Mitigation in Urban Centres	RMIT, EIT	Cross-cutting, Health, Mobility, Sust. Urb.
link	Urban dynamics: Spatial Accessibility and Real estate	RMIT, EIT	Carbon neutrality, Economy, Mobility, Sust. Urb.

Figure 5: Udeemy platform. Source: [Udeemy](https://www.udemy.com/).

Udeemy is a vast online learning platform that offers a wide variety of courses created by independent instructors. It provides flexible and affordable learning options on numerous topics. However, topics such as urban resilience, social justice in cities, and climate neutrality in cities are almost not covered there to date. Udeemy courses are often practical and accessible, with features such as lifetime access, diverse teaching styles, and the ability to learn at one's own pace. This platform is particularly valuable for those seeking specific skills or knowledge areas in a more informal educational setting. Unlike Coursera, edX and FutureLearn, Udeemy's courses can vary significantly in quality due to the range of instructors, but they are typically more affordable and flexible. Despite its limitations in covering certain urban topics, it is still interesting to acknowledge the platform's specificities.

Particularity and differences: Udeemy's key strength lies in its flexibility and affordability. The platform allows learners to purchase individual courses and access them for life, which is different from the subscription or certification model seen on Coursera and edX. While Coursera and edX focus on academic rigor and structured learning, Udeemy offers a more informal and diverse range of courses taught by industry professionals. This makes Udeemy an excellent choice for learners seeking practical, hands-on skills in specific areas, though the quality can be more variable compared to the more standardized offerings on Coursera, edX and FutureLearn. Unlike the other platforms presented, Udeemy is not strictly speaking a MOOC platform, it operates on a different business model and does not offer free courses. While initial prices may appear high, Udeemy frequently offers promotions during which most course prices drop to around €9.

Table 5: Summary of relevant online courses on Udeemy.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	A Guide for Sustainable Urban Development	Prof. M. Senthil	Sust. Urb.

link	Introduction to Sustainable Urbanism	Dr. Sheeba Valsson	Sust. Urb.
link	Learn Urban Planning Concepts	Prof. M. Senthil	Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.

Each of these platforms offers unique advantages and caters to different aspects of urban planning and sustainability education. Coursera and edX provide high-quality, research-driven courses with strong academic credentials. Udemy offers practical, flexible, and affordable learning experiences. FutureLearn emphasizes social learning and community engagement. Understanding these differences allows us to leverage the most suitable aspects of each platform to enhance the design and delivery of the UP2030 training program, ensuring it meets the diverse needs and constraints of urban planning professionals.

2.1.2 [Key organizations and Institutions with dedicated training platforms](#)

In the landscape of online education, various entities have recognized the value of developing dedicated platforms to host their training content. These platforms serve as centralized hubs for disseminating knowledge, skills, and resources tailored to specific needs and audiences. This section explores key organizations and institutions that have opted to establish their own training platforms, with a primary focus on MOOCs. Through an examination of their approaches and offerings, this exploration sheds light on the diverse strategies employed to deliver targeted and impactful learning experiences. The following lines explore some of these independent platforms and courses (All the courses mentioned in this section are listed in Appendix 1):

- 1) Among the global climate resilience actors working with cities, [the network C40](#) operates a [knowledge hub](#), primarily delivering resources through guides and articles. They also offer two courses through their platform, powered by Open edX. This platform showcases several compelling features and a high level of flexibility. It seamlessly integrates various content formats, such as videos, articles, guides, and quizzes. Moreover, it includes a dedicated "discussion" section, promoting learner interaction. This platform design offers flexibility for content production and enhances convenience for students.

Figure 6: C40 Cities platform interface. Source: [C40](#).

Table 6: Online courses on C40 Cities Platform.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Clean Construction E-learning Course	C40 org	Sust. Archi.
link	Inclusive Climate Action	C40 org	Social Justice

2) Moving from a city network to an institutional key player in the fight against climate change, the **United Nations (UN) UNITAR platform** offers courses developed through various UN projects. These courses cover a wide range of topics, organized into six thematic areas (see Table 7). Among the 368 online courses available for free in English, one of the most relevant to the UP2030 European Project MOOC is the “Cities and Climate Change” course, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 7: UNitar platform interface. Source: [UNitar](https://www.uncclearn.org/).

Table 7: Summary of relevant online courses on Unitar.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Carbon Taxation	United Nations	Carbon neutrality, Governance
link	Cities and Climate Change	United Nations	Climate Change
link	Making Cities Resilient: Developing Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience Strategies	United Nations, UNDRR	Resilience
link	Resilience of Local Governments: A multi-sectoral approach to integrate public health and disaster risk management	United Nations, UNDRR	Health, Resilience

- Looking to Europe, the [NetZeroCities Mission Portal](#) serves as a repository for various learning materials within its "knowledge section," encompassing a diverse array of content, including 83 videos covering a range of topics. Notably, it features a single MOOC program, the **Positive Energy District (PED) Start Guide**. Developed by the Atelier project and sponsored by the City Net Zero Centre of Expertise at the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, this free, short e-learning course offers valuable learning opportunities. It includes additional features such as recommended supplementary content and quizzes to enrich the learning experience.

Figure 8: PED Start Guide MOOC interface. Source: [PED Learning](#).

Table 8: Online course on the NetZeroCities Mission Portal.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Positive Energy Destricts - PED Start Guide	Atelier & CoE City Net Zero Amsterdam Univeristy	Energy, Smart Cities

- 4) Another interesting independent platform is the [Urban Shift](#) platform, a collaborative effort by the UN Environmental Programme (UNEP), World Resource Institute (WRI), C40, and ICLEI, which serves as the home for their **City Academy** program. This program comprises eight courses, detailed in table 9, each addressing different urban topics. These courses typically span is between 6-8 hours and are accessible at no cost in six different languages. In addition to video content, the platform offers supplementary features such as written documents and tests, enhancing the overall learning experience for participants.

Figure 9: Urban Shift course on City Academy platform. Source: [Urban Shift](#).

Table 9: Summary of relevant online courses on Urban Shift platform.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Accessing Urban Climate Finance	Urban Shift, online city academy, ICLEI and others	Cross-cutting, Economy
link	Accommodating Urban Growth	Urban Shift, online city academy, C40, Marron Institute NY	Cross-cutting, Growth
link	Circular Economy Strategies for Sustainable Development	Urban Shift, online city academy, ICLEI and others	Cross-cutting, Economy, Social Justice
link	Green & Thriving Neighbourhoods	Urban Shift, online city academy, UN	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Economy, Governance, Social Justice
link	Integrated Climate Action Planning	Urban Shift, online city academy, C40	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Integrated Urban Planning	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Nature-Based Solutions	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	NBS

link	Urban Biodiversity	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	Biodiversity, Cross-cutting
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- 5) The [Urban Resilience Hub](#), which is **UN-Habitat**'s technical partner for urban resilience, also develops free online training programs. These programs are hosted on the **City Resilience Training (CRT) platform**, a collaborative learning platform run by the UN Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Center of Excellence of the University of Geneva. The platform offers courses on how to create more sustainable futures for cities. Notably, it features a highly relevant course titled "Introduction to Urban Economic Resilience Diagnostics and Action Planning in the context of COVID-19."

Figure 10: City Resilience Training platform interface. Source: [Urban Resilience Hub](#).

Table 10: Summary of relevant online courses on City Resilience Training platform.

Link	Course title	Institution	Main Topics
link	Accelerating, Benchmarking and Communicating Smart and Sustainable Cities' Transitions	Urban Resilience Hub, WeGO	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Resilience, Smart Cities, Social Justice
link	Development of SDG Voluntary Local Reviews in UNECE Region	Urban Resilience Hub, UNECE	Climate Change, Governance, Social Justice
link	Introduction to Urban Economic Resilience Diagnostics and Action Planning in the context of COVID-19	Urban Resilience Hub	Economy, Health, Resilience

- 6) Finally, it is important to mention that a significant amount of qualitative content is also available on public platforms like YouTube. Some organizations, such as UN-Habitat, have opted to share their educational content freely on public platforms like the aforementioned. They have amassed a collection of over 1,100 videos, organized into playlists on their [@unhabitatglobal](https://www.youtube.com/@unhabitatglobal) YouTube channel. These playlists cover specific events like COP28, interviews with experts, and series of lectures organized in seasons, such as their latest Global Urban Lectures – Season 6, which features 11 videos, each approximately 15 minutes long. Since 2013, this UN channel has garnered over 1.7 million views and accumulated 16.500 subscriptions, making it a valuable knowledge resource. While this approach makes the content highly accessible, it may lack the structured learning experience offered by dedicated training platforms.

Figure 11: UN-Habitat Worldwide Youtube page. Source : [@unhabitatglobal on Youtube](https://www.youtube.com/@unhabitatglobal).

This section has showcased a variety of organizations and institutions offering dedicated training platforms, offering a spectrum of approaches and resources tailored to specific needs, and covering topics in urban planning, climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice. From structured MOOCs with interactive features to repositories of articles, guides, and videos, the diversity of platforms reflects the richness of options available to learners. Each platform offers distinct features that cater to different preferences and demands, highlighting the versatility and accessibility of online education in this field.

2.2 Identifying gaps and opportunities

When analyzing the landscape of existing online courses related to urban resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice, several significant gaps and opportunities have been identified, particularly in terms of content and methodology. The methodology for this analysis included a comprehensive review of existing courses online, specifically focusing on the three main pillars of UP2030 and courses available in English, primarily within European contexts, and targeting city practitioners. The analysis also involved platform evaluations, stakeholder consultations, and input from experts within the consortium. Addressing these gaps will ensure that the UP2030 training program meets the specific needs of city practitioners and effectively fills the existing gaps in online education.

2.2.1 Target audience

The primary target audience for the MOOC consists of city practitioners, including urban planners, municipal officials, and policymakers who are directly involved in urban development and planning processes. Many of these professionals have been working in the field for many years and may not always be aware of the latest scientific conclusions, tools, and technologies. They often have full-time jobs and significant responsibilities, leaving them with limited time for studying.

City practitioners: City practitioners face several challenges, including limited time for professional development, rapidly evolving urban issues, and the need to balance multiple responsibilities. Consequently, they require training that is concise, practical, and immediately applicable.

Consultants: In addition to city practitioners, the MOOC aims to reach urban planning consultants who advise cities on development projects. Consultants need to stay informed about the latest trends, tools, and methodologies to provide relevant and effective guidance.

Needs and challenges: Both city practitioners and consultants share common needs and challenges, such as:

- **Time constraints:** The need for flexible, self-paced learning options that accommodate busy schedules. The training must be concise and not overly long, providing essential information in a time-efficient manner.
- **Practical relevance:** Emphasis on actionable knowledge and skills that can be directly applied to urban planning projects.
- **Holistic approach:** Comprehensive content that addresses the interconnected aspects of climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice.
- **Accessibility:** Ensuring that the training is accessible to a wide audience through multiple languages and user-friendly platforms. It must cater to individuals with diverse backgrounds and varying levels of expertise.

2.2.2 Content gaps and opportunities

While there are numerous courses available on individual aspects of urban planning, there is a noticeable lack of comprehensive courses that address climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice in an integrated manner. This fragmented approach can result in practitioners lacking a complete understanding of how these elements interact within the context of urban planning and development. Addressing these gaps

requires a more integrated and thorough educational approach that focuses on depth, practical examples, and avoiding unintended consequences.

Gaps and opportunities for content development and integration include:

- **In-depth focus:** Providing more detailed content on underrepresented topics such as social justice in urban planning, equitable climate action, and inclusive resilience strategies. Courses should also include training on relevant tools and techniques, enabling practitioners to apply theoretical concepts effectively in real-world scenarios.
- **Case studies and best practices:** Incorporating detailed case studies and best practices from diverse cities to demonstrate practical applications and successful implementations of these principles. This helps bridge the gap between theory and practice.
- **Avoiding undesirable effects:** Offering training that prepares practitioners to recognize and avoid undesirable effects such as greenwashing, maladaptation, gentrification, and other unintended consequences. This ensures a comprehensive understanding of the subject.
- **Adaptation to local contexts:** Providing content that can be tailored to different geographical and cultural contexts, ensuring relevance and applicability for practitioners working in varied environments.
- **Holistic integration:** Developing courses that cohesively integrate climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice, illustrating the interdependencies and synergies between these areas. This holistic approach helps practitioners understand and address the complex interactions within urban planning and development.

2.2.3 [Methodological gaps and opportunities](#)

The methodology employed by many existing courses often does not align well with the practical needs and professional demands of city practitioners. Traditional academic approaches may not fully resonate with practitioners who require more applied, hands-on training.

Opportunities for methodological improvements include:

- **Clear course selection:** With the proliferation of online learning resources, the diversity of offerings has become a barrier to effective learning. The abundance of options can lead to confusion and counterproductivity for city practitioners seeking relevant training. There is an opportunity to streamline the learning process and offer a cohesive learning experience by providing a clear, comprehensive program that covers essential topics under one umbrella.
- **Practical focus:** Many online courses are primarily designed for students rather than practitioners already working full time on the field, resulting in content that is often more theoretical and less immediately applicable. This is a significant gap because practitioners require content that is ready to be applied in real-world scenarios. Designing concise and clear courses that emphasize practical skills and real-world applications, rather than purely theoretical knowledge, is essential. This approach recognizes the time constraints faced by city practitioners and ensures that the training delivers actionable insights in a time-efficient manner. Additionally, providing training on technical tools through tutorials enhances the practical applicability of the content.
- **Flexible learning formats:** While most MOOCs are indeed flexible, many specific courses are not self-paced or have short deadlines to encourage users to pay for a subscription fee. This presents a gap, as city practitioners require the ability to learn at their own pace due to their busy schedules.

Offering modular courses, self-paced learning, and micro-learning segments can accommodate these needs. This flexibility allows practitioners to access relevant content when it best fits their schedule, promoting continuous professional development without disrupting daily responsibilities.

- **Continuous professional development:** There is a need for ongoing learning and skill development opportunities, which include access to updated content, new case studies, and emerging best practices in the field. Continuous professional development ensures that city practitioners remain up-to-date with the latest trends, technologies, and methodologies. This ongoing learning enhances their effectiveness in addressing complex urban challenges.
- **Supportive environment and community engagement:** Many existing courses lack a supportive learning environment that fosters community engagement, networking, and collaboration among practitioners. There is an opportunity to create a community-focused learning space where peer-to-peer learning is encouraged. This approach enables practitioners to share insights, seek advice, and collaborate on projects, enhancing the overall learning experience and fostering a sense of community within the field of urban planning.

By addressing these content and methodological gaps, the training program can better meet the needs of city practitioners, equipping them with the knowledge, skills, and tools necessary to effectively integrate climate neutrality, resilience, and social justice into their urban planning practices. This approach not only enhances individual competencies but also contributes to the broader goal of sustainable and equitable urban transformation, providing practitioners with practical, actionable knowledge and skills to address the challenges of urban planning in a time-efficient and effective manner.

3 MOOC program design

This chapter delves into the detailed design of the UP2030 MOOC program, focusing on various aspects crucial for its effectiveness and impact. From establishing clear learning objectives to outlining the pedagogical approach and module overview, each subsection offers insights into the comprehensive structure of the MOOC program. By carefully crafting the design elements, the aim is to ensure that the program meets the diverse learning needs of city practitioners while fostering engagement, accessibility, and knowledge acquisition.

Based on the identified gaps and opportunities, this course has been designed to maximize the integration between carbon neutrality, resilience, and social justice, addressing the issue of educational silos. Emphasizing a multidisciplinary approach, the program design moves beyond technical (easy-fix) solutions to the complex urbanization issue of responding to climate change. For example, the concept of the "Smart City," initially outlined as one of the pillars in the GA, was excluded from the UP2030 MOOC. This exclusion is due to its association with increasing cities' efficiency, often at the expense of resilience and social justice. Recent literature and academic advances in urban studies and climate resilience have highlighted the issues of green and climate gentrification associated with climate resilience and smart cities approaches when social justice is not central to implementations. Given this emerging consensus and critique of the smart city concept, the UP2030 MOOC focuses on the interplay between carbon neutrality, resilience, and social justice.

The following subsections explore the key components of the UP2030 MOOC program design, detailing how it will facilitate meaningful learning experiences and contribute to the overarching goals of the UP2030 project.

3.1 Learning objectives

The learning objectives are related to each group of potential profiles interested in the UP2030 MOOC. On one side, the aim is to address city practitioners, and on the other, to reach consultants. University students are not the main target group of this training. Because of this orientation, the learning objectives are twofold: first, to mainstream the relationship between carbon neutrality, resilience, and social justice among cities and introduce the tools that can be used; second, to enhance consultants' critical view of the needed link among these concepts and enable them to use more open and user-friendly tools.

The goal of the first part of the UP2030 MOOC is to familiarize participants with the 5UPs step-by-step holistic approach outlined in the UP2030 project. By empowering them with comprehensive knowledge and practical skills, the program aims to equip participants with the confidence and competence to take action through the step-by-step governance process of the 5UPs. This includes ensuring a strong understanding of key urban challenges and providing accessible training on existing tools and processes.

In addition to theories and tools, the UP2030 MOOC seeks to inspire participants through both conceptual aspirations and concrete examples of successful urban transformations. By showcasing inspiring concepts such as the "15-minute city" and the "sponge city," as well as empirical case studies from project implementations, the UP2030 MOOC aims to provide both inspiration and practical guidelines through examples.

Upon completion of the MOOC, participants will be equipped with the necessary theoretical background, technical tools, and practical inspirations to drive urban transformations centered on resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice. The program aims to empower participants to make a meaningful impact in their work with cities, contributing to sustainable and equitable urban development.

3.2 [Pedagogical approach](#)

The pedagogical approach of the training program is designed to provide effective learning experiences that resonate with city practitioners' needs and challenges. Central to this approach is the recognition that traditional, in-person academic methodologies may not fully meet the practical demands of working professionals. Conversely, current short online courses often do not provide enough in-depth content to be considered effective. Therefore, in light of the gaps and opportunities within the online education offerings, the pedagogical framework of the UP2030 MOOC emphasizes several key principles to ensure that the training is accessible, engaging, and actionable.

3.2.1 [Accessibility](#)

The training program prioritizes accessibility and inclusivity, not just by being open and online, but by enabling attendees from diverse backgrounds, experiences, and learning preferences to align through introductory modules. These modules clearly explain "what is what" about carbon neutrality, resilience, and social justice, aligning participants' knowledge while preparing the ground for the more technical parts. Furthermore, efforts have been made to ensure that the content is always presented in clear and straightforward language, free from unnecessary academic jargon or technical slang.

Recognizing practitioners' busy agendas, the courses will be rich in content and composed of dozens of concise videos. This ensures that participants can choose and engage with the videos they truly need, customizing the learning path according to their knowledge and limited timeframes. Moreover, efforts will be made to make most of the content available in a wide range of European languages to increase its accessibility.

Additionally, efforts will be made to include features that support accessibility for people with disabilities. This may include providing subtitles for individuals with auditory impairments and ensuring screen-reader compatibility for those with visual impairments. These measures aim to ensure that all participants can fully engage with the material, regardless of their physical abilities.

3.2.2 [Active learning and engagement](#)

A storytelling approach, inspired by the 5UPs methodology, will guide participants through a step-by-step process that is easy to follow. This approach draws on real case studies from the UP2030 project, providing practical examples of the concepts and tools covered in the training. While interactive elements such as quizzes and case studies are desired to promote deeper understanding and engagement, their implementation will depend on the platform's capacity to offer these features. Nonetheless, the courses will aim to incorporate practical exercises and real-world examples to facilitate hands-on learning and application of theoretical knowledge.

3.2.3 [Practical relevance](#)

The training program emphasizes the practical relevance of the content, moving beyond theoretical discussions to focus on real-world applications. The transdimensional approach, central to the training, underscores the interconnectedness of resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice in addressing urban challenges comprehensively. By offering a comprehensive course with numerous technical tutorials for various tools (in addition to theoretical and case study content), participants can customize their learning

path by choosing which tools to see implemented, grounding the UP2030 MOOC in real-world applications. This is why the program aims to provide clarity amidst the abundance of available learning content.

By adopting a pedagogical approach grounded in accessibility, engagement, and practical relevance, the training program aims to empower city practitioners and consultants with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to drive sustainable urban transformations.

3.3 [Program overview and structure](#)

The MOOC's training content is structured to guide participants from initial inspiration and theoretical introduction to the implementation of concrete tools and actions to guarantee impact. This approach ensures a cohesive learning journey, from theory to practice, where each step logically builds upon the previous one, following the 5UPs approach of the project.

In alignment with the project's GA and the work of the project partners, the figure below illustrates the UP2030 MOOC structure. It organizes the project workflow and results within three modules, following the 5UPs approach. Each module comprises a mix of videos that adhere to three main pedagogical approaches: theoretical, technical tutorials, and case studies, as seen on Figure 12.

Theoretical videos: These videos will focus on presenting theoretical content, making both basic and complex concepts accessible to a wide audience. The aim is to create highly pedagogical videos that are dynamic and well-produced, facilitating a clear understanding of the material. These capsules will be developed in collaboration with the academic experts within the consortium, ensuring high-quality and accurate content.

Technical videos: These videos will concentrate on the technical solutions provided by various tools, divided into three subcategories:

- **Introduction videos:** Short videos designed to clearly explain the purpose of each tool.
- **Tutorial videos:** Comprehensive, detailed tutorials that enable users to fully understand and utilize the tools to their full potential.
- **Real case example videos:** Videos that demonstrate the practical application of the tools through real-world examples.

Case study videos: These capsules will showcase real case examples of the implementation of UP2030 methodologies, particularly through the experiences and projects of city partners. These videos will illustrate the practical application and impact of the methodologies in real urban settings.

Figure 12: Alignment of MOOC structure with GA and UP2030 workflow.

Regarding the structure of the UP2030 MOOC, the first module (Figure 13) focuses on understanding and building (or consolidating) city visions (corresponding to the "UPDating" project work package (WP)). Participants gain a thorough understanding of the relevant theoretical concepts, which are essential to avoid hasty decisions, and then establish clear goals and visions. Setting adaptive pathways toward these goals and identifying any gaps or barriers that need to be addressed is the last step in this first module, before jumping into action.

Figure 13: MOOC Module 1 structure overview.

The second module (Figure 14) shifts to capacity building and tools for implementation (corresponding to the "UPskilling and UPgrading" WPs). Participants will follow technical courses explaining tools and UP2030 solutions, and learn from case study examples how these have been implemented.

Figure 14: MOOC module 2 structure overview.

After understanding tools and implementations, the last module (Figure 15) introduces amplifying solutions and impacts (corresponding to the project UPScaling and UPTaking WP). The video courses will explain how to scale-up and integrate solutions across different sectors, providing methods for dissemination and impact amplification through knowledge transfer involving a wider community of practice.

Figure 15: MOOC module 3 structure overview.

Given that much of the material for the MOOC is based on project outcomes that are still in development, the program's design remains flexible to accommodate these evolving elements. Additionally, the distribution of tools across the modules is an ongoing process, carried out in close collaboration with technical partners and TUD, which is responsible for tool coordination. Taking these factors into account, figures 13, 14 and 15 provide an overview of the program's design as of June 2024.

3.4 Potential additional content

In addition to the videos, the MOOC may incorporate a variety of additional content to enhance the learning experience and provide comprehensive educational resources. While the inclusion of this content is still under consideration, the potential elements being explored include:

- **Links to additional resources:** Direct links to supplementary materials and external resources that complement the video content.
- **Links to other project results:** Connections to related projects and their outcomes, such as the carbon neutrality tools guide developed by colleagues from UCAM, the social justice guide by TUD, the upscaling platform by ICLEI, and the financial toolkit developed by GGGI.
- **Direct links to tools:** Easy access to tools discussed in the videos, allowing participants to explore and use them directly.
- **Quizzes and tests:** Interactive quizzes and tests to reinforce learning and assess understanding.
- **Certification option:** Potential for participants to earn a certificate upon successful completion of the course.

- **Discussion section:** A forum for participants to engage in discussions, share insights, and ask questions.
- **Infographics:** Visual aids to help illustrate key concepts and data.

The inclusion of these additional elements will be adapted based on the final content available at the time of the MOOC's publication, depending on the development and availability of other project results. The technical feasibility of certain features will also be considered.

4 Implementation plan

This chapter outlines the comprehensive plan for implementing the MOOC program within the framework of the UP2030 project. It details the timeline for development and integration, the resources required, the current stage of progress, the criteria for platform selection, and the strategies for disseminating the program to the target audience.

Figure 16: Implementation timeline.

4.1 Timeline and contingency plan

Given that much of the MOOC content is dependent on the project's results and outcomes, a significant portion of the material is still in the development phase. This includes the majority of the tools and the ongoing implementation phase with the city partners. Consequently, the timeline for producing some of the content remains flexible. However, the production of videos is scheduled to commence in October 2024.

Theoretical courses videos: These are prioritized as the first phase of production. The aim is to complete the recording of these videos between the beginning of October 2024 and the end of December 2024, in collaboration with academic partners. This schedule allows ample time for post-production, visual effects, translation, and other necessary enhancements to ensure the content meets high-quality standards.

Technical videos and tutorials about the tools: Production for these videos will begin concurrently with the theoretical course videos but will extend throughout the project timeline. Given that many tools are still under development and are expected to remain so when the MOOC is ready for publication, a continuous follow-up will be necessary with the technical partners. Coordination with TUD, responsible for overseeing the tools, will ensure the timely production of these videos as soon as the tools are ready.

Case study videos and examples: Starting in October 2024, the production of content available at that stage will be organized with the city partners, in collaboration with the RCities Network. As the implementation with the city partners will not be fully completed by then, the production of these videos will be based on their progress and will adapt accordingly.

Technical development of the MOOC platform: The technical development to support the MOOC will commence in August 2024. This ensures that the platform will be ready to host and integrate the content as it is produced, providing a seamless and efficient user experience upon release.

By adhering to this timeline, the MOOC program aims to systematically integrate with the UP2030 project, ensuring that the content is both timely and relevant to the project's goals and outcomes.

4.2 [Content resources](#)

The content for the MOOC program will be created primarily by the partners within the consortium, utilizing their expertise and the results of their work. Additional content from open sources may be used if necessary, but the primary material will be developed internally to ensure alignment with the project's goals and standards.

4.3 [Current stage](#)

This entire document provides a comprehensive overview of the preparation work and design of the MOOC, representing the current stage of development. Regarding content production, the progress can be detailed as follows:

Masterclasses: Masterclasses have been organized for knowledge alignment and internal capacity building within the consortium. Recordings of these sessions, focusing on the three pillars of the project—resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice—are available to all partners on the internal platform. While these recordings could serve as material for the MOOC, the goal is to produce final videos with a higher quality of presentation. Future masterclasses may be organized in collaboration with RCities and Fraunhofer if any gaps or additional needs are identified within the consortium.

Technical solutions videos: Every technical partner has been contacted to evaluate their capacity to present their tools in a comprehensive video format. This includes explaining the tool's purpose, identifying its gaps, providing a complete tutorial on its use, and offering examples. As of May 2024, 10 out of the 40 tools included in the project are fully developed and ready for application. Despite many tools still being in the development phase, content has been gathered for 17 tools, comprising 12 introduction videos, 7 tool tutorials, 4 example videos showcasing real cases, and 7 hybrid videos that present the current development stage of the tools. Particular attention will continue to be paid to the progress of these tools to ensure the timely production of training videos as they reach completion.

Challenges: A significant challenge is the need to provide training content on tools and project outcomes while adhering to the production deadline of July 2025. Given that some of the project's outcomes and tools will not be fully developed by this time, ensuring the training program is comprehensive and up-to-date will be difficult. This requires careful planning and ongoing coordination with all partners to address gaps and incorporate the most current information as it becomes available. Compromises and solutions may need to be discussed with the partners who will be the latest to deliver content, ensuring that the training program remains relevant and valuable despite these timing constraints.

Another challenge is gathering quality training content from technical partners who may not be accustomed to creating such material and who are already managing significant workloads. Ensuring that these partners can contribute effectively without compromising the quality or delaying the timeline is crucial.

Additionally, due to the project's size and the volume of content and tools developed, another challenge will be to present this material in a way that educates MOOC users effectively without overwhelming or confusing them. It is essential to make this content accessible and user-friendly while still linking to other project products to guarantee the best user experience.

4.4 [Platform selection](#)

The MOOC will be hosted on an internal platform provided by UIC University. This decision was made in consultation with the involved partners and notably through a workshop organized by ICLEI about UP2030 platforms. The decision is primarily based on the available budget, which does not support the development and maintenance of a dedicated platform. Utilizing UIC's platform ensures long-term support, flexibility, accessibility, and credibility for the program. Additionally, the potential use of specific tools like Open edX for the development of the interface is being explored.

4.5 [Dissemination plan](#)

The dissemination plan for the MOOC aims to maximize its reach and impact by leveraging the visibility of several UP2030 platforms and networks, as well as the extensive networks of its numerous partners, particularly those directly in contact with cities.

The details and implementation of this dissemination plan will be further discussed and refined in the coming months until December 2024 with the colleagues from DreVen and the Dissemination & Communication WP.

Utilizing partner networks and platforms: The MOOC will benefit from the visibility of the UP2030 platforms and the networks of its numerous partners. These networks, especially those directly connected with cities, will play a crucial role in reaching the target audience.

Independent videos and broad availability: Many capsules from the MOOC will be made available independently on various platforms. Each of these capsules will include credits that refer viewers to the full MOOC, creating a seamless link to the broader training program. Short and engaging videos will be extracted from the produced content to facilitate easy sharing and audience expansion.

Conferences and forums: At a more advanced stage of development, the MOOC can be showcased at various conferences and forums. This will help to raise awareness and promote the training program among key stakeholders in urban planning and sustainability.

Launch events and recurrent introductions: Events could be organized to mark the launch of the training program. These events, potentially recurring, will introduce the MOOC to participants, create networking opportunities, and facilitate exchanges of ideas and experiences.

Encouraging participant advocacy: The final module of the MOOC will encourage participants to share the training with their colleagues and networks. This aligns with the UP-Taking philosophy of the 5UPs approach, aiming to extend the impact of the project through peer advocacy and community engagement.

5 Sustainability plan

This chapter outlines the strategies to ensure the MOOC remains sustainable over time, focusing on financial sustainability, long-term viability, and contingency planning.

5.1 Financial sustainability

As the training program must remain freely accessible to everyone, it will not generate direct revenue. The long-term financial sustainability of the MOOC will be secured through its integration into UIC's platform, which provides continuous management and support.

If future costs are identified, two potential funding sources could be considered:

- **Certificate of fee:** Charging a fee for the optional certificate of completion, providing a revenue stream without compromising free access to the core content.
- **Event participation fees:** Implementing fees for participation in special events, workshops, or webinars related to the MOOC's content. These events could offer additional value and services, helping to cover any incidental management costs.

This approach ensures that the MOOC remains financially sustainable while maintaining its commitment to providing free educational resources.

5.2 Long-term viability and exploitation

The long-term viability of the MOOC will be ensured through several strategic measures:

Integration with UIC's platform: The MOOC will be embedded within UIC's platform alongside other educational content, ensuring continuous visibility and promotion. This integration guarantees sustained support and management from UIC, leveraging their established infrastructure and expertise.

Collaborations and partnerships: Opportunities for collaboration with other projects and platforms that host similar content will be explored to create synergies. Both academic and industry partnerships could be developed, enhancing the MOOC's reach and impact. These collaborations will allow for resource sharing and mutual promotion, further solidifying the MOOC's presence in the educational landscape.

Community building: A strong community of learners and educators will be cultivated, particularly through the UP-Taking module. This community will include new participants and alumni, fostering an environment of continuous learning and sharing. By building and maintaining this network, the MOOC will benefit from ongoing engagement and support, ensuring its relevance and vitality.

Regular content updates: To keep the content current and relevant, regular updates will be made based on feedback from participants and the expertise of UIC's team.

5.3 Contingency plan

Technical assistance and support: Given that the MOOC will be embedded within UIC's platform, it will benefit from UIC's personnel resources and technical assistance in case of any technical issues. This support ensures that any technical difficulties encountered can be promptly addressed, minimizing disruptions and maintaining a smooth user experience.

Adaptability to project outcomes: The final content of the MOOC may vary depending on the timing and outcomes of other project deliverables, such as tool development and the creation of city typologies. Flexibility will be built into the project timeline to accommodate these dependencies, allowing for adjustments to be made as necessary.

Ongoing coordination with partners: Effective management of these variables will require ongoing coordination with all project partners. Regular updates and communication will help ensure that any delays or changes in the development of related project components are promptly addressed, allowing for timely incorporation into the MOOC.

6 Next steps

Technical development of the MOOC platform (August 2024): Starting in August 2024, the technical development of the MOOC's platform will commence. This platform will host video capsules and additional content, including documents, links, quizzes or tests, and discussion sections. The aim is to create a comprehensive and user-friendly interface that facilitates learning and interaction.

Continuous follow-up with partners: A continuous follow-up process will be maintained with all partners to stay updated on their development progress and their capacity to deliver the required training content. This ongoing coordination is crucial to ensure that all necessary materials are available and up-to-date.

Development of video scripts (until October 2024): By the end of October 2024, the scripts for each video should be precisely developed to ensure the content is optimal, and the presentation is engaging. This preparation phase is essential to guarantee that the material is well-structured and aligns with the training objectives.

Recording of videos (starting October 2024): The recording of videos will begin in October 2024. All theoretical videos are expected to be recorded by the end of December 2024. Simultaneously, technical videos about the tools and case study videos will start production. However, the timeline for these videos will be extended based on the availability and readiness of the content.

Post-production process: Post-production of the videos, including quality improvement, visual effects, translations, and other enhancements, will be a continuous process starting from October 2024. This phase will ensure that the final videos are polished and meet high-quality standards.

Dissemination plan (by December 2024): By the end of December 2024, the dissemination plan must be detailed and organized in collaboration with the WP partners. This plan will ensure a strategic and coordinated approach to promoting the MOOC and engaging the target audience effectively.

Launch of the MOOC (July 2025): The first version of the MOOC is expected to be available online by July 2025. This version will incorporate all the developed content and will be accessible to users.

7 Conclusion

This report has outlined the comprehensive plan for creating a valuable educational resource that addresses the needs of city practitioners and aligns with the broader goals of the UP2030 project. It marks the first phase of the MOOC development, with its actual production directly following this deliverable.

The MOOC aims to bridge a significant gap between city practitioners and solution providers, whether technical or academic. It also addresses the confusion and overwhelming nature of the current landscape of training content, which is not always well-adapted to every audience. This program seeks to make the content highly accessible and easy to understand for a wide audience, with a particular focus on city practitioners. The goal is to create a program that is not only accessible but also comprehensive, eliminating the need for additional courses on similar topics by offering a holistic approach. This approach is based on three pillars: resilience, climate neutrality, and social justice, and includes three dimensions of training: theoretical knowledge, practical tools, and inspirational real-life examples.

While the extensive content ensures the program's completeness, it also presents a significant challenge. Gathering and coordinating this diverse content is essential to maintain clarity and avoid overwhelming the audience. The richness of the program lies in its ability to provide a wide array of information while remaining focused and coherent for its users.

The implementation plan, detailed in this report, provides a clear roadmap for developing, producing, and disseminating the MOOC. It highlights the importance of continuous collaboration, flexibility in content development, and strategic dissemination to maximize the program's impact.

The sustainability plan ensures the MOOC's long-term viability by integrating it into UIC's platform, exploring potential funding sources, and maintaining regular content updates. These measures will help sustain the program's relevance and accessibility over time.

Looking ahead, the next steps involve finalizing the technical development of the platform, producing high-quality video content, and executing a comprehensive dissemination plan. By adhering to these plans and maintaining ongoing coordination with partners, the MOOC is poised to become a cornerstone resource for urban practitioners across Europe.

In conclusion, the MOOC program represents a significant contribution to the field of urban planning, providing practitioners with the knowledge, tools, and inspiration needed to drive sustainable urban transformations. Through this collaborative effort, the UP2030 project aims to create lasting impacts on urban development, fostering cities that are resilient, climate-neutral, and socially just.

Appendix

Appendix 1

Table 11: Summary of relevant online courses table.

Link	Course title	Platform	Institution	Main Topics
link	Building Inclusive Cities: Tackling Urban Inequality and Segregation	edx	TUD	Social Justice
link	Built environment sustainability assessment	edx	UPV	Cross-cutting, Economy, Energy, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities and Climate Change: Mitigation and Adaptation	edx	MIT	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Health, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities and the Challenge of Sustainable Development	edx	SDG academy	Sust. Urb.
link	CitiesX: The Past, Present and Future of Urban Life	edx	Harvard University	Cross-cutting, Governance, Mobility, Social Justice
link	Co-Creating Sustainable Cities	edx	TUD, WUR	Energy, Food, Governance, Sust. Urb.
link	Co-Creating Sustainable Cities	edx	TUD, WUR	Cross-cutting, Energy, Food, Governance, Mobility
link	Designing a Climate-Neutral World: An Introduction	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Sust. Urb.
link	Designing a Climate-Neutral World: Taking Action	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Governance
link	Designing Climate-Neutral Buildings and Transport	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Mobility, Sust. Archi., Sust. Urb.
link	Designing Climate-Neutral Industry and Electricity Generation	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy

link	Edesign for Cities and Suburbs	edx	UBC	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Environmental Gamechanger – Lead the Way to Sustainable Development	edx	WUR	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Food and Nutrition Security in Urbanising Landscapes	edx	WUR, UN environment, Landscape academy	Cross-cutting, Food, Governance, Resilience, Sust. Urb.
link	Global housing design	edx	TUD	Sust. Archi.
link	Nature-based Urban Regeneration	edx	RWTH Aachen University	Governance, NBS, Regenerative
link	New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges	edx	TUD	Cross-cutting, Social Justice
link	Passive Urban Cooling Solutions	edx	World Bank Group	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience, NBS,
link	Professional Certificate in Climate-Neutral World: Theory, Applications and Taking Action	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Energy, Governance, Mobility
link	Reclaiming Broken Places: Introduction to Civic Ecology	edx	Cornell University	Biodiversity, Cross-cutting, Governance, Social Justice
link	Rethink the city: New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges	edx	TUD	Cross-cutting, Social Justice
link	Shaping Urban Futures	edx	SDG academy	Cross-cutting, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Smart and Sustainable Cities: New Ways of Digitalization & Governance	edx	TUD	Governance, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Cities	edx	SDG academy	Cross-cutting, Governance, Health, Resilience, Social Justice

link	Sustainable Urban Development	edx	TUD & WUR, AMS	Cross-cutting, Growth, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Urban Environments	edx	Trinity College	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience, Sust. Urb.
link	The Transition to the Decarbonised Economy of Tomorrow	edx	TUD	Carbon neutrality, Energy
link	Urban Ecology Design	edx	TUD	Biodiversity, NBS, Regenerative
link	Urban Rewilding: Restore Your Local Ecosystem	edx	WUR	Biodiversity, Regenerative
link	Urban Upgrading for Inclusion, Sustainability and Resilience in a time of Global Pandemics	edx	World Bank Group	Governance, Health, Resilience, Social Justice
link	Vision 2030	edx	ZHAW	Cross-cutting, Food, Growth, Health, Resilience, Smart Cities, Social Justice
link	Cities and Consumption: Urban Sustainability and the Sharing Economy	Coursera	Lund University	Cross-cutting, Economy, Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Cities, Climate and Change: Pathways and Opportunities	Coursera	Lund University	Carbon neutrality, Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Economy, Sust. Urb.
link	Climate change and Indigenous People and local communities	Coursera	UAB	Climate Change, Governance, Social Justice
link	Gestion des infrastructures urbaines - partie 1	Coursera	EPFL	Cross-cutting, Energy, Mobility, Resilience
link	Greening the Economy: Sustainable Cities	Coursera	Lund University, WWF, ICLEI	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Economy, Sust. Urb.

link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 1	Coursera	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Resilience	Health,
link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 2 : Theories, models and tools	Coursera	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience	Health,
link	HEALTHY URBAN SYSTEMS - PART 3 : Design and policies	Coursera	UNIL	Cross-cutting, Governance, Smart Cities	Health,
link	Innovative Governance of Large Urban Systems	Coursera	EPFL	Cross-cutting, Governance, Regenerative	Economy,
link	Planning for Climate Change in African Cities	Coursera	Erasmus University Rotterdam	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience	
link	Street Experiments for Sustainable and Resilient cities	Coursera	TUM, EIT	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.	Mobility,
link	Sustainable Neighborhoods	Coursera	Johns University Hopkins	Cross-cutting, Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.	
link	Sustainable Regional Principles, Planning and Transportation	Coursera	Johns University Hopkins	Governance, Mobility, Sust. Urb.	Growth,
link	Sustainable Transportation Networks and Streetscapes	Coursera	Johns University Hopkins	Growth, Resilience, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.	Mobility,
link	Sustainable Urban Regeneration	Coursera	Bocconi University	Carbon neutrality, Economy, Governance, Regenerative, Resilience, Social Justice	
link	Transportation, Sustainable Buildings, Green Construction	Coursera	Johns University Hopkins	Carbon neutrality, Social Justice, Sust. Archi., Sust. Urb.	

link	Urban Climate Governance: Towards 1.5° Celsius Alignment	Coursera	Lund University, WWF	Cross-cutting, Energy, Governance, Mobility, Sust. Urb.
link	Urban Nature: Connecting Cities, Sustainability and Innovation	Coursera	Lund University	Economy, Governance, NBS
link	Urbanisation and Health - Promoting Sustainable Solutions	Coursera	University of Copenhagen, EIT, Politecnica Madrid, University of Coimbra	Cross-cutting, Health, NBS, Social Justice
link	Clean Construction E-learning Course	C40 platform	C40 org	Sust. Archi.
link	Inclusive Climate Action	C40 platform	C40 org	Social Justice
link	Carbon Taxation	Unitar	United Nations	Carbon neutrality, Governance
link	Cities and Climate Change	Unitar	United Nations	Climate Change
link	Making Cities Resilient: Developing Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience Strategies	Unitar	United Nations, UNDRR	Resilience
link	Resilience of Local Governments: A multi-sectoral approach to integrate public health and disaster risk management	Unitar	United Nations, UNDRR	Health, Resilience
link	Accessing Urban Climate Finance	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, ICLEI and others	Cross-cutting, Economy
link	Accommodating Urban Growth	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, C40, Marron Institute NY	Cross-cutting, Growth
link	Circular Economy Strategies for Sustainable Development	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, ICLEI and others	Cross-cutting, Economy, Social Justice

link	Green & Thriving Neighbourhoods	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, UN	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Economy, Governance, Social Justice
link	Integrated Climate Action Planning	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, C40	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Integrated Urban Planning	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	Cross-cutting, Sust. Urb.
link	Nature-Based Solutions	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	NBS
link	Urban Biodiversity	shiftcities	Urban Shift, online city academy, World Resources Institute	Biodiversity, Cross-cutting
link	Positive Energy Districts - PED Start Guide	pedlearning	Atelier & CoE City Net Zero Amsterdam Univeristy	Energy, Smart Cities
link	Accelerating, Benchmarking and Communicating Smart and Sustainable Cities' Transitions	City Resilience Training	Urban Resilience Hub, WeGO	Climate Change, Cross-cutting, Resilience, Smart Cities, Social Justice
link	Development of SDG Voluntary Local Reviews in UNECE Region	City Resilience Training	Urban Resilience Hub, UNECE	Climate Change, Governance, Social Justice
link	Introduction to Urban Economic Resilience Diagnostics and Action Planning in the context of COVID-19	City Resilience Training	Urban Resilience Hub	Economy, Resilience, Health,
link	A Guide for Sustainable Urban Development	Udemy	Prof. M. Senthil	Sust. Urb.
link	Introduction to Sustainable Urbanism	Udemy	Dr. Sheeba Valsson	Sust. Urb.
link	Learn Urban Planning Concepts	Udemy	Prof. M. Senthil	Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.

link	Achieving Transitions to Zero Carbon Emissions and Sustainable Urban Mobility	FutureLearn	UCL, ICLEI, EIT, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Bringing Urban Nature Into the Cities of Tomorrow	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	NBS, Resilience
link	Building Belonging in a Globalised and Mobile World	FutureLearn	EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice
link	Changing Urban Travel Behaviour for a Low-Carbon Transition	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Creating Ethical and Sustainable Cities at the Local Level	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	Electrification of Urban Mobility: How to Get it Right	FutureLearn	EIT	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Mobility
link	Equity in Informal STEM Learning: Using the Equity Compass	FutureLearn	UCL	Governance, Social Justice
link	Ethical Cities: Shaping the Future of Your City	FutureLearn	RMIT	Governance, Social Justice
link	Fostering Inclusive Citizen Engagement in Urban Development	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, Social Justice
link	Introduction to Climate Justice and Equity	FutureLearn	University of Glasgow	Cross-cutting, Economy, Energy, Food, Governance, Social Justice
link	Reducing Carbon Footprints: Taking Action for a Sustainable Future	FutureLearn	Warwick University	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Governance
link	Smart Urban Green Infrastructure	FutureLearn	EIT, ACCESS Aalto University	Carbon neutrality, Cross-cutting, Mobility, NBS, Smart Cities, Sust. Urb.
link	Sustainable Cities: Governing Urban Adaptation Under Climate Change	FutureLearn	University of Groningen & Global Center on Adaptation	Cross-cutting, Governance, Resilience,

				Smart Cities, Social Justice, Sust. Urb.
link	The Challenge of Clean Growth and Clean Cities	FutureLearn	Manchester Metropolitan University	Carbon neutrality, Energy, Growth, Smart Cities
link	The New European Bauhaus: Concept, Movement, and Opportunities	FutureLearn	EIT, New European Bauhaus	Governance, NBS, Sust. Urb.
link	Transforming Urban Mobility: Components of Transport Planning for Sustainable Cities	FutureLearn	UCL, GIZ, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Transforming Urban Mobility: Introduction to Transport Planning for Sustainable Cities	FutureLearn	UCL, GIZ, TUMI	Carbon neutrality, Mobility
link	Transit-Oriented Development for Climate Mitigation in Urban Centres	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT	Cross-cutting, Health, Mobility, Sust. Urb.
link	Urban dynamics: Spatial Accessibility and Real estate	FutureLearn	RMIT, EIT	Carbon neutrality, Economy, Mobility, Sust. Urb.
link	Nature Based Metropolitan Solutions	TUD Platform	TUD	Cross-cutting, NBS